

SLEEP QUALITY OF MUNICIPAL HEALTH WORKERS OF LYING-IN CLINICS IN NUEVA VIZCAYA

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ABSTRACT

Sleep problems affect 45% of the global population, posing risks to health, relationships, and workplace performance. In the Philippines, over half of respondents face sleep issues, with healthcare workers particularly impacted due to stressors and demanding schedules. Using a quantitative descriptive-comparative design, this study aimed to understand sleep quality factors and their effects, focusing on municipal health workers in some municipalities in Nueva Vizcaya. The study profiled purposively selected health workers in MHOs in lying-in clinics in Nueva Vizcaya by various demographics and analyzed their sleep quality (efficacy, latency, duration, disturbance, medication, subjective quality, daytime dysfunction). It also compared sleep quality across profiles and produced IEC material on sleep quality as an outcome. Researchers conducted one-on-one interviews, ensuring confidentiality and informed consent and a survey questionnaire to gather data. Results shows that most of the respondents are middle-aged, female, college graduates, and nurses. Over half have mid-career service, and nearly half can save sufficiently. In terms of sleep quality, 60.4% experience poor sleep quality, with issues like delayed sleep, short duration, and disturbances. Age and socio-economic status affect sleep quality, while sex, job position, and service length do not. Strategies such as health assessments, sleep initiatives like consistent routines and stress management, community support, and further research are recommended to explore contributing factors and interventions.

Keywords: *Healthcare workers, occupational health, sleep interventions, sleep problems, sleep quality*

INTRODUCTION

According to Buysse (2014), sleep quality plays a crucial role in physical and mental well-being, with poor sleep often leading to cognitive impairments, mood disorders, and decreased performance. Worldwide, sleep problems constitute a global epidemic that threatens health and quality of life for up to 45% of the world's population (World Sleep Society, 2023). According to Nelson et al. (2021), sleep loss and sleep quality are global health concerns in which poor sleep quality has significant adverse health outcomes. This is concerning because sleep quality is vital to one's health and well-being. In fact, Itani et al. (2017) found in a meta-analysis that poor sleep quality was significantly associated with increased risk of all-cause mortality, cardiovascular diseases, and depression.

Abadilla (2023) stated that the Philippines has the biggest sleep problems in Southeast Asia, with 56% of respondents experiencing sleep problems. Among the population, sleep problems are common in health workers who face many stressors, and many studies have shown that sleep plays a major role. Consequently, health workers had poorer sleep characteristics among multiple sleep dimensions, which significantly affect their relationship with their family, clients, co-workers, and superiors. Anwar (2018) concurs with this, saying that viral loneliness and social rejection are triggered by poor sleep, wherein sleep-deprived people feel lonelier and less inclined to engage with others. Furthermore, a report by Philippine Society of Sleep Medicine (2022) emphasized that sleep disorders are underdiagnosed in the country, especially among Filipino workers who often normalize poor sleep due to long working hours and night shifts.

Additionally, lack of sleep in healthcare workers leads to safety dangers. According to the study of Shaik et al. (2022) in the United States of America, exceeding scheduled work hours led to 36% of physicians committing serious medical errors and a fivefold increase in diagnostic errors. There was also a 61% rise in needle-sick injuries and a doubled risk of driving accidents after long shifts, highlighting the significant risks associated with extended work hours. Evidently, the relationship between shift work, poor sleep quality, and risk of medication errors represents a crucial point for all health professionals' communities. Medication errors and sleep deprivation of health workers had a great effect on the patient, and it is indeed a big problem if these things were to happen (Di Simone et al., 2020).

According to Pitchler and Morris (2020) sleep deprivation resulting either from poor choices related to sleep habits or to occupational requirements such as shift work is a common cause of sleep- and sleepiness-related determinants in the workplace. Sleep deprivation negatively impacts a wide range of employee performance, health, and well-being issues including immune defense reaction, cardiovascular functioning, metabolic disorders, mood disorders; affective reactivity, motivation, subjective effort, accidents in the workplace, and performance on many types of vigilance and more complex cognitive tasks. In addition, daytime sleepiness is related to higher mortality rates, cardiovascular disease and diabetes, and fatigue-related accidents. This wide range of effects related to poor and inadequate sleep has led some to declare a sleep crisis as a public health issue.

Therefore, the researchers conducted this study to identify the factors that contribute to sleep quality and to examine its effects on the respondents. The Province of Nueva Vizcaya was chosen as the study site, with municipal health care workers as the target population, given the limited number of studies conducted on this group within the province. Although global and national awareness of sleep-related concerns has grown, there remains a significant research gap concerning the sleep quality of specific healthcare groups, particularly municipal health workers and staff in lying-in clinics. These professionals frequently work in resource-limited settings, manage irregular schedules, and face heavy workloads—factors that can negatively impact their sleep health. While existing research has focused primarily on the general health workforce or hospital-based personnel, little is known about the unique sleep challenges experienced by those serving in community-based primary care facilities. Addressing this gap is crucial to developing targeted interventions that support the well-being of health workers and enhance the quality of patient care in primary healthcare settings.

Statement of the Problem

This research aimed to determine the sleep quality of Municipal Health Workers of lying-in clinics in Nueva Vizcaya during the 2nd semester of the academic year 2024 – 2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the demographic profile of the health workers in MHOs with lying-in clinics in terms of:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Sex;
 - c. Educational attainment;
 - d. Position;
 - e. Length of service; and
 - f. Socio-economic status?
2. What is the sleep quality of the MHO workers in terms of:
 - a. Efficacy;

- b. Latency;
 - c. Duration;
 - d. Disturbance;
 - e. Sleep medication;
 - f. Subjective sleep quality; and
 - g. Daytime dysfunction?
3. Is there a significant difference in the sleep quality of the MHO workers in lying in clinics when grouped according to their demographic profile variables?
 4. What Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) Material on sleep quality can be produced based on the findings of this study?

METHODOLOGY

The design that was employed in this study is quantitative descriptive-comparative. The research locale of this study covers Aritao, Quezon, Santa Fe, Solano, and Villaverde. These municipalities were chosen because their Municipal Health (MHO) offers day-night services. Moreover, these towns are characterized as “active” as they accommodate check-ups, administration of vaccines, laboratory studies, most especially normal spontaneous delivery (NSD) and other emergency cases. According to Brinkhoff (2023), the total population of Nueva Vizcaya as of 2020 is 497,432. The respondents of this research study are the municipal health workers such as the dentist, medical technologist, midwife, nurse, nursing aides, nutritionist, pharmacist, and physicians that are working in the said municipalities that have lying-in clinics and who are directly giving care or are in contact with their clients. These respondents rotate their duties every two weeks, consistently covering both morning and night shifts- 12 hours, before exchanging schedules to accommodate clients in the evening. Purposive sampling was used to select these participants.

Table 1

Population of Research Respondents of Every Municipality

Municipalities	Population of MHWs	Percent of Total MHWs
Aritao	18	17.82
Quezon	15	14.85
Santa Fe	23	22.78
Solano	29	28.71
Villaverde	16	15.84
TOTAL	101	100

The research instrument employed in this study was a survey questionnaire. Part I asked about the demographic profile of the respondents. This specifically would determine the respondents' age, sex, educational attainment, position, length of service, and socioeconomic status. Part II was an adopted questionnaire. Following a thorough search and screening of questionnaires related to sleep quality, the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) developed by Buysse et al. (1989) was selected for adoption in this research. Notably, the PSQI has also been utilized in studies involving health workers. The scale has 10 questions with domains, which include sleep efficacy, latency of sleep, sleep duration, disturbance of sleep, utilization of sleep medicine, subjective data of sleep quality, and daytime dysfunction.

Upon the approval of the municipal mayors, chosen health worker respondents were each given a copy of the informed consent form (ICF) inviting them to participate in the study. The researchers explained the purpose of the study to each respondent and assured the privacy and confidentiality of the gathered information. The data on profile variables were analyzed using

frequency and percent. Mean and standard deviation were used for the sleep quality index of the respondents. The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) was scored using seven component scores, ranging from 0 (no difficulty) to 3 (severe difficulty). The component scores were added to produce a global score (range 0 to 21). The worse sleep quality is indicated by higher scores. The sleep quality of the respondents when grouped according to the profile variables was compared using independent samples *t*-test for sex and one-way analysis of variance for age, educational attainment, position, length of service, and socio-economic status.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. Respondents' Demographic Profile

Among the 101 respondents, the majority population of MHO workers are middle-aged adults with 58.42% (59). In terms of sex, about three-fourths of the respondents are female, with 77.2% (78), with male respondents comprising 18.8% (19). Almost all the respondents are college graduates, 97.03% (98). Nurses had the highest population in terms of position with 48.51% (49), followed by midwives with 24.75% (25). Nutrition officers, midwife-nurses, pharmacy assistants, and radtechs had the lowest population in terms of position, with 0.99 % (1). In terms of length of service, almost half of the health workers are in their mid-career (5-15 years), 47.52 % (48). It is also shown that 44.55% (45) of the respondents have sufficient income and can invest and save. However, it is also evident that 12.88% (13) of respondents claimed their income is just enough for family needs and can hardly save.

Section 2. Sleep Quality Index of MHO Health Workers in Lying-In Clinics

Table 2

Sleep Quality Among the MHO Health Workers in Lying-In Clinics and Its Sleep Categories

PSQI Component Scores	Mean Score	Description
Habitual Sleep Efficiency	0.81	No Difficulty
Sleep Latency	1.40	Mild Difficulty
Sleep Duration	1.40	Mild Difficulty
Sleep Disturbances	1.10	Mild Difficulty
Use of Sleep Medication	0.26	No Difficulty
Subjective Sleep Quality	0.79	No Difficulty
Daytime Dysfunction	0.54	No Difficulty

Legend: 0 - 0.9: No difficulty, 1 - 1.9: Mild Difficulty, 2 - 2.9: Moderate Difficulty, and 3: Severe Difficulty

The table shows that the respondents had no difficulty in maintaining good sleep, with a value score of 0.81. These results were in contrast to the study by Cheng and Cheng (2016), where it is indicated that workers with night shifts were found to have the shortest duration of sleep and with greater risks for sleep problems such as insomnia. It is also necessary to note that lifestyle habits such as smartphone use at bedtime, water ingestion at bedtime, and occupational stress were associated with sleep efficiency among workers (Ikeda et al., 2022). This finding suggests a potentially positive sleep environment or individual factors contributing to healthy sleep patterns within this group.

The respondents had a mild difficulty in the component of sleep latency, with a value score of 1.40. This means that the Municipal Health Office (MHO) health workers had a problem in initiating sleep, or they took longer to get their desired sleep. This contributing factor supports the study of Suni and Rehman (2023), which stated that the sleep quality of an individual is considered to be poor if it takes a person longer than 30 minutes to fall asleep, if the individual wakes up multiple times

throughout the night, or if it takes longer than 20 minutes to fall back asleep after waking up. Even if a person gets the recommended number of hours of sleep, eventually, the person would probably feel tired the next day. These findings are also in line with a study by Niu et al. (2017) that found that in the rotating shift group, staff members working the night shift had a shorter sleep onset latency (SOL) on Day 2 than those working the day or evening shift. Another study by Ruggiero et al. (2012) found that health workers working the night shift were drowsier after work for the first two days. These nurses switched from sleeping at night and waking during the day to the reverse sleep/wake cycle on the first day of their night shift (Kudielka et al., 2007). Chronic weariness and a rise in the amount of sleep needed for recuperation were also said to be caused by the accumulation of sleep deficits and deprivation (Lamond et al., 2003; Muecke, 2005; Rotenberg et al., 1998, cited in Kudielka et al., 2007). Therefore, it is probable that the nurses in the rotating shift group who worked the night shift experienced weariness as a result of their accrued sleep debt, which decreased the amount of time between bedtime and the start of sleep on the second day of the night shift.

This implies that understanding the interaction of these occupational stressors with individual lifestyle factors and pre-existing illnesses is crucial. Gaining a deeper insight into these contributing factors will empower one to advocate for and implement evidence-based interventions aimed at improving the sleep quality and overall health of these MHO health workers. To better understand this, future research might include detailed sleep diaries, actigraphy, and qualitative interviews.

Regarding the sleep duration of MHO workers, most workers had mild difficulty, with a 1.40 value score, which means some MHO workers experience insufficient sleep. These points indicate that they are not getting enough sleep overall. This is similar to the study of Stimpfel et al. (2020), which describes sleep duration of nurses across health care and community settings and concludes that nurses are sleeping, on average, less than recommended amounts before work.

It can be seen that there is also a mild sleep disturbance in sleep among the respondents, with a value of 1.10. According to Habiburrahman et al. (2021), both sleep quality and sleep disturbances exhibit significant correlations with depression, fatigue, and general stress. Furthermore, the study reported that the association was more significant in sleep quality compared to quantity. Additionally, Al-Hrinat et al. (2024) found that sleep disturbances play a crucial role in mediating the relationship between night shift stress and quality of life. Increased night shift stress was linked to greater sleep disturbances, which subsequently resulted in lower quality of life. The findings emphasized the need to acknowledge and address the distinct challenges experienced by nurses working night shifts.

Thus, evaluating both environmental factors within their workplace and individual factors, such as stress or underlying health conditions, that might be contributing to these sleep disruptions, could be involved. Highlighting the vulnerability of night shift workers to even seemingly minor disruptions in their sleep patterns can serve as a crucial link between occupational stress and diminished well-being. Recognizing the distinct challenges faced by Health workers working night shifts, these emphasize the importance of acknowledging and proactively addressing even mild sleep disturbances to safeguard their overall health and quality of life, and help to modify these disturbances to improve the sleep quality of the MHO health workers.

The MHO health workers' value score on the use of sleep medication is 0.26, which falls under the category of "no difficulty." Despite this categorization, it is still alarming that some respondents rely on pharmacological management. This suggests a preference for medication over non-pharmacological approaches, which is ironic given their medical training typically emphasizes non-

pharmacological interventions as the first line of treatment.

According to the study of Alghamdi et al. (2024), there is truly a self-reported rate of use of sleep medication; however, it was also lower than the other sleep parameters. The reported level was nevertheless significant, with 8.6% reporting use at least once a week and 3.5% reporting use three or more times a week. In a related study, Dorrian et al. (2011) found that stress and workdays were significant predictors of sedative use. Nurses and midwives may use caffeine to compensate for reduced sleep, especially on workdays, and sleeping pills to cope with their daily work-related stress. Sleep medication can improve the mental quality of life of an individual, but it may degrade the physical quality of an individual due to its adverse effects (Sasai et al., 2010).

Despite facing sleep problems, health workers demonstrated a tendency to avoid frequent reliance on sleep medications, likely prioritizing non-pharmacological approaches, as evidenced by the low number of individuals utilizing pharmacological management. However, this finding remains significant, as the resort to medication by some individuals may indicate more severe underlying issues, such as the influence of demanding work schedules and occupational stress. While sleep medication can offer perceived short-term mental health benefits, potential physical side effects necessitate careful consideration.

The respondents had a value of sleep quality of 0.79, which falls in no difficulty, despite the objective measures indicating poor sleep quality. This indicates a discrepancy between subjective and objective sleep quality. In contrast with this, the study by Deng et al. (2020) showed that the higher the job stress is, the poorer the sleep quality is. This discrepancy between subjective and objective data could be attributed to several factors, such as MHO workers might have adapted to chronic sleep deprivation, leading to a normalization of poor sleep. In addition, they might be underreporting their sleep issues due to a belief that sleep problems are a normal part of their demanding jobs, or a perceived stigma, whether internalized, perceived, or anticipated, is associated with self-reported characteristics of sleep deficiency (Nwanaji-Enwerem, 2022).

The respondent value score of 0.54 showed no difficulty. This indicates that even though there are some sleep issues, this does not significantly impact the daily activities of MHO workers. This contrasts with the findings of Harlynadia and Basrowi (2023), which indicated that poor sleep quality due to excessive daytime sleepiness was significantly more common among healthcare shift workers than non-shift workers.

The analysis of the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) data reveals that the average global PSQI score is 6.30 (SD = 2.85), indicating that most respondents experience poor sleep quality. In fact, 60.4% are classified as poor sleepers (PSQI >5), while only 39.6% have good sleep quality (PSQI ≤5). Among the PSQI components, the most common sleep issues include sleep latency (1.40 - Mild difficulty), sleep duration (1.40 - Mild Difficulty), and sleep disturbances (1.10 - Mild Difficulty), suggesting that many respondents take longer to fall asleep, do not get enough sleep, and experience interruptions during the night compared to the other components.

According to Ghalichi et al. (2013), a person's occupation is believed to affect the prevalence of sleep disorders. The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), a reliable method for measuring sleep quality, identifies scores over 5 as indicative of poor sleep (Buysse et al., 1989). Studies on healthcare workers have shown varying prevalence of poor sleep quality. Ghalichi et al. (2013) found that healthcare workers (43%) had poor sleep quality, while Soliman et al. (2024) reported a higher prevalence (73.5%) with an average PSQI score of 6.33 (SD = 2.07). Additionally, a recent study by Soliman et al. (2024) has shown that sleep problems are common among healthcare workers. It also

correlates with burnout, leading to poor performance. Moreover, the prevalence of sleep disorders among shift workers was significantly higher than day workers. Therefore, addressing the underlying health conditions and determinants of poor sleep quality can enhance sleep quality among healthcare workers.

Section 3. Significant Difference in the Sleep Quality of the MHO Workers in Terms of Demographic Profile Variables

Table 3

Sleep Quality of the MHO Workers When Grouped According to Their Demographic Profile Variables

Profile Category	Groups	Mean	SD	F-value / t-value	p-value
Age	Young Adults (≤ 30)	6.32 ^A	2.75		
	Middle-Aged Adults (31-45)	6.81 ^A	2.67		
	Older Adults (>45)	4.36 ^B	3.25	4.433*	0.014
Sex	Female	6.50	2.83	1.869 ^{ns}	0.423
	Male	5.63	3.09		
Position	Nurse	6.11	1.97	1.458 ^{ns}	0.129
	Midwife	5.93	3.25		
	Medical Technologist	5.95	2.64		
Length of Service	Early Career (≤ 5 years)	6.31	2.96	0.199 ^{ns}	0.820
	Mid-Career (6-15 years)	6.46	2.81		
	Late Career (>15 years)	5.80	3.85		
Socio-economic Status	Have sufficient income, can invest & save	5.41 ^C	3.15	4.169*	0.019
	Have income but no investment, can save a little	6.90 ^B	2.81		
	Income just enough for family needs, can hardly save	7.73 ^A	1.56		

In terms of age, the table shows that the highest mean in sleep quality was for middle-aged adults ($M = 6.81$, $SD = 2.67$) followed by young adults ($M = 6.32$, $SD = 2.75$), and the lowest mean is for older adults (>45 years) ($M = 4.36$, $SD = 3.25$). The ANOVA result revealed that there was a significant difference in sleep quality, $F = 4.433$, $p = 0.014$; Scheffe post hoc comparison indicated that older adults had a significantly lower mean of the global PSQI score component than middle-aged adults or young adults. This indicates that older adults had better sleep quality than middle-aged adults or young adults. In terms of sex, the higher mean score was for females ($M = 6.50$, $SD = 2.83$). However, the t-test result ($t = 1.869$, $p = .423$) disconfirmed the significant difference between the sleep quality of male and female respondents. In terms of position, the highest mean was nurse ($M = 6.11$, $SD = 1.97$), followed by the medical technologist ($M = 5.95$, $SD = 2.64$) or Midwife ($M = 5.93$, $SD = 3.250$); nevertheless, the ANOVA ($F = 1.458$, $p = 0.129$) did not demonstrate a significant difference in sleep quality across these job positions of MHO Health workers. Likewise, in terms of the length of service of the MHO workers, the highest mean was mid-career (6-15 years) with ($M = 6.46$, $SD = 2.81$), but there is no significant difference in sleep quality. In terms of socio-economic status, the highest mean is for workers whose income was just enough for family needs and could hardly save ($M = 7.73$, $SD = 1.56$), while those with sufficient income to invest and save had the lowest mean ($M = 5.41$, $SD = 3.15$). Scheffe post-hoc tests indicated that the health worker with sufficient income to invest and

save was having the best sleep quality, followed by the workers that have income but no investment, can save a little ($M= 6.90$, $SD = 2.81$) had a good sleep quality, on the other hand, the workers whose income was just enough for family needs and could hardly save has a bad sleep quality compared to the two.

The observed poor sleep quality among older MHO workers contradicts findings from the research of Zhou et al. (2020), which demonstrated that older age is associated with poorer sleep quality among frontline health professionals. Sleep quality generally decreases with age, as the biological age increases, with older adult respondents scoring higher on most of the components of the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) compared to younger adults (Kim et al., 2021). Given the poorer sleep quality observed among older MHO workers, targeted interventions such as sleep hygiene education, stress management programs, and ergonomic workplace adjustments may be beneficial. The significant difference in terms of socioeconomic status is also confirmed by the study of Sosso et al. (2021), which indicates that lower socioeconomic status is typically associated with poor sleep quality. This also pointed out that it is possible that individuals with lower income experienced physical fatigue, leading to improved sleep onset, compared to those with higher incomes experiencing increased stress related to financial management. However, they also highlighted that a further investigation is needed to understand the underlying factors contributing to this unexpected result.

Section 4. Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) Material on Sleep Quality

The Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) Material in the form of a poster about the sleep quality of the Municipal Health Office (MHO) health workers highlights the importance of sleep for MHO's health workers and provides practical tips for improving sleep quality. It emphasizes that good sleep is crucial for cognitive function, mental and physical health, and overall well-being. It also reveals that many MHOs experience sleep challenges, including difficulty falling asleep, insufficient sleep duration, and frequent nighttime disturbances, and it also includes the other component of sleep quality that is not affected and somehow needs to be maintained. It also illustrated through a pie graph the prevalence of poor sleep quality among Municipal Health Office (MHO) health workers, given that a significant 60.6% of MHO workers report poor sleep quality according to the global PSQI scores. The poster encourages MHOs to prioritize self-care through establishing consistent sleep schedules, creating relaxing bedtime routines, optimizing sleep environments, limiting screen time before bed, and practicing relaxation techniques, and prioritizing sleep as a fundamental aspect of self-care, advocating for 6 to 8 hours of sleep for good health. Contact information for the SMU Guidance Office is also provided to further support the MHO workers in addressing their problems with sleep latency, sleep disturbance, and sleep duration, as these components indicate significant problems with their sleep.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

1. The Municipal Health Office healthcare workers consisted mainly of female workers, middle-aged adults (31-45 years old), dominantly nurses, and in their mid-career, working in MHO for 6-15 years, and have sufficient income, can invest, and save.
2. Overall, the average global PSQI score indicates that most respondents experience poor sleep quality. The most common sleep issues include sleep latency, sleep duration, and sleep disturbance, suggesting that many respondents take longer to fall asleep, do not get enough

sleep, and experience interruptions during the night. However, the use of sleep medication and daytime dysfunction did not present significant difficulties, indicating that sleep issues have a limited impact on daily activities for most respondents.

3. Age had a significant effect on sleep quality, with older adults (>45 years) having significantly better sleep quality compared to young adults and middle-aged adults. Additionally, socio-economic status was a significant factor, with workers whose income was just enough for family needs and could hardly save reporting the bad sleep quality, while those with sufficient income to invest and save had good sleep quality. However, sex, job position, and length of service did not show a significant impact. Additionally, educational attainment could not be used due to the distribution of responses.
4. An IEC material in the form of a poster was developed. It emphasizes the critical importance of sleep for cognitive function, physical and mental health, and overall well-being. It provides practical recommendations for improving sleep habits, aiming to enhance the health and service quality of municipal health workers.

Recommendations

1. **Comprehensive Health Assessment:** While age and socio-economic status play a crucial role in influencing sleep quality among MHO workers, they do not significantly determine poor sleep quality on their own. Hence, it is also important to consider other contributing factors to poor sleep quality. Future researchers can develop a comprehensive health assessment that assesses and includes sleep history, physical and mental health screenings, stress level factors, occupational health, and lifestyle factors to better understand the factors affecting the sleep quality among MHO health workers.
2. **Health Worker Sleep Initiatives:** Collaborating with the MHO workers can educate them about the discrepancies in their sleep quality. Even with the high demands of their work, facilitating all the individuals of their community, Municipal Health Office (MHO) workers can prioritize their sleep by establishing consistent sleep routines and creating a relaxing bedtime environment. These initiatives can include awareness campaigns, identifying factors that contribute to poor sleep quality, such as time management, stress management, and technology usage.
3. **Environmental Awareness:** By collaborating with the higher organization, the community can show its support by understanding the demanding nature of MHO workers' jobs and the potential impact on their sleep. Providing educational materials on the significant others can also promote community-wide initiatives that encourage healthy sleep habits for everyone by creating a conducive sleep environment for the MHO workers.
4. **Future Research:** Future researchers can build upon this study by expanding and delving deeper into the specific factors that contribute to sleep problems among MHO workers, such as work-related stress or individual health conditions. They can also delve more into the discrepancies of the data to other studies and how it affects the sleep quality of individuals. They can also conduct long-term studies to assess the impact of interventions and develop new strategies to improve sleep quality.

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